

Andragogy Methods in Strengthening Training for School Principles to Improve Motivation, Leadership, And Communication

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ABSTRACT The purpose of this study was to determine the effectiveness of using the andragogy method in increasing motivation, leadership and communication after the implementation of Principal Strengthening Education and Training which was held in October 2019 at the Center for Development and Empowerment of Educators and Education Personnel, Business and Tourism, Depok, WestJava. The method used in this research is to use a qualitative approach with descriptive methods, data collection techniques are carried out by questionnaires, observation and documentation studies. The subjects of this study were all participants in the training for strengthening principals in Banten Province in 2019 batch IX, totaling 159 people. The results showed that with the andragogy method, the understanding of the material received a good response from the participants, so as to increase motivation, leadership and communication in the school they lead. It is hoped that in addition to developing motivation, leadership and communication, school principals are also able to develop their abilities in the fields of facilities and infrastructure, entrepreneurship, character development, managerial, as well as in other fields so that the quality and quality of schools will increase

KEYWORDS: Andragogy; headmaster; training

I. INTRODUCTION

As a leader in educational institutions, the role of the principal is needed so that the existing resources at the educational institution he leads are able to become schools that produce graduates who are able to compete, think critically, be more creative and are able to develop their creativity in accordance with the goals, vision and mission of the school. To realize this, then as a learning center, schools must have principals who are able to realize and manage the vision, mission, goals and objectives that have been set. This is to implement the Regulation of the Minister of National Education Number 13 of 2007 concerning Standards for Principals/Madrasah, that: "a school principal is expected to have personality, managerial, entrepreneurial, supervisory, and social competencies, where the principal must have the competence and ability to carry out his duties, roles, and functions as school principals.

Wahjosumijo stated that: "the principal as a leader must have a special character that includes personality, basic skills, professional experience and knowledge, as well as administrative and supervisory knowledge. The leadership of a principal as a driving factor to realize the vision, mission, goals and objectives. Principals are required to have strong management and leadership skills. Principal as school leaders, given a mandate by the government to improve the quality of education by using their role in carrying out a task.

develop teaching and learning process. To improve the quality of learning, it is necessary to have supporting factors consisting of educators to carry out their duties as teaching staff and carry out their functions professionally" (Wahjosumidjo, 1999). Principals must be able to mobilize school resources, planning, evaluating programs, curriculum, learning human resource management, facilities, learning resources, finance, student services, community relations, and creating a conducive atmosphere in the school environment. In addition, the role of the principal is also a determinant of the success of education in schools, because the principal is the center and source of teaching and learning activities, besides that the principal is an influential component in improving the quality of education in schools. This shows that the ability or professional competence of a school principal greatly determines the quality of education. The position of the principal is a professional position to continue to develop in accordance with the development of the need for quality Human Resources and other resources to compete in a better and competitive direction in regional, national and international forums. The progress of the quality of education is largely determined by the quality of its human resources.

Therefore, to achieve a high level of education, a professional education system is needed and is able to carry out its duties and functions with the aim of being supported by educators and educational staff as well as professional school principals which are determined by performance. One of the most serious problems in education in our country today is the low quality of education in various types and levels of education. Many parties argue that the low quality of education is one of the factors that hinders the provision of human resources who have the expertise and skills to meet the demands of nation building in various fields, the principal as a leader must be able to provide guidance and supervision, increase the willingness of educational staff, open two-sided communication. direction and delegate tasks. Wahjosumidjo suggested that "the principal as a leader must have a special character that includes personality, basic skills, experience and professional knowledge, as well as knowledge of administration and supervision". (Wahjosumidjo, 1999)

The abilities that must be realized by the principal as a leader can be analyzed from personality, knowledge of education, school vision and mission, decision-making abilities and communication skills. The principal's personality as a *leader* will be reflected in the characteristics of (1) honest, (2) confident, (3) responsible, (4) willing to take risks and decisions, (5) big hearted, (6) stable emotions, (7) exemplary. Seeing the many tasks of the principal, a principal is required to have managerial abilities. Otherwise, the school will not be able to manage and the school atmosphere will not be conducive. The principal always tries to devote his abilities in carrying out his duties to achieve goals. (Dindin, 2020). The ability that must be possessed by a leader in this case the principal is to have a personality that is a role model for his subordinates, the ability to motivate, make decisions, communicate and delegate authority. It is at this stage that the principal's leadership role is needed. The principal must act decisively against violations that occur, so that all components in the school provide optimal service to students and school residents.

The position of the principal is a professional position to continue to develop in accordance with the development of the need for quality Human Resources and other resources to compete in a better and competitive direction in regional, national and international forums. Therefore, the competence of the principal needs to be developed to suit the needs. The development of these competencies can be developed in various ways, in various ways, including through education and training. Alternative solutions for school principals who have not met One of the competencies is through education and training. Gradually and continuously the competence of school principals must be improved through training and education to strengthen principals. "The obligation of prospective principal teachers to take part in the Education and Training of Principal Candidates before serving as Principal has been regulated since 2010 through Article 6 of the Regulation of the Minister of National Education Number 28 of 2010 concerning Assignment of Teachers as Principals of Schools/Madrasah" (Husni, Aan., Sururi, 2020)

To realize this, the government has established a program called education and training and strengthening school principals for school principals who have officially become school principals. The implementation of the education and training is submitted to the education and training organization (LPD)

which has been determined by the Director General of Teachers and Education Personnel. One of the LPDs assigned to carry out this task is the LPD of Pamulang University which is tasked with carrying out training and strengthening of school principals for the Banten Province level. The learning strategy implemented in the school principal strengthening training carried out by each generation at Pamulang University is emphasized on the andragogy approach, considering that from the age of these participants in class IX in 2019 there were 1 person aged between 30-35 years (1%), aged between 36-40 years are 12 people (7%), and over 40 years old was 146 people (92%). The application of the andragogy approach in the implementation of training and education to strengthen principals is expected to be able to increase motivation, leadership style and communication of principals when they return to duty after carrying out the training. In addition, it is also hoped that school principals will be able to improve the quality and quality of other education.

Various studies have been carried out by previous researchers, namely by Adang Rukmana with the title "The influence of the principal's leadership style and teacher work motivation on teacher performance", which was published in the *Ikopin Scientific Management Coepetition Journal* Vol 9 number 1 May 2018 pages 77-93, and research conducted by Rizki Ainul Islamiah with the title "Application of the Andragogy Approach in the Learning Process of Knitting Training at the Smart House for the Eyes of the Literature", which was published by the *Electronic Journal of PLS students* Vol. 5 No. 5 of 2016. However, the difference in this study is how the principals apply the andragogy approach in improving motivation, leadership and communication after attending school principal strengthening training.

The formulation of the problem in this study is: How is the effectiveness of the andragogy method on principals in developing motivation, leadership and communication after attending educational training and strengthening school principals, therefore, this study aims to determine the effectiveness of the andragogy method after training for strengthening the principal, then it is necessary to conduct research on the effectiveness of the andragogy method in education and training in increasing motivation, principal leadership, and principal communication after attending school principal training and education.

II. METHOD

This research was conducted for 1 (one), from August 2020 to July 2021 for principals throughout Banten Province after attending Education and training for strengthening school principals Batch IX in 2019 at P4TK Bispar Sawangan Depok. The subjects taken in this study were all trainees from batch IX, totaling 159 people. The type of research used is descriptive method using a qualitative approach, data collection techniques are carried out by questionnaires, observations and documentation studies. Qualitative research approach is a research procedure that produces descriptive data in the form of written or oral words carried out using questionnaires, observations, and studies. documentation, then interpreted with each other so that a formulation and analysis of existing problems is obtained. (Moleong, 2018) Based on this description, it can be concluded that descriptive research method is a form of pouring thoughts that describes, describes, and reports on the state of an object from what it is. researched based on the facts and information obtained.

III. RESULT

a. The effectiveness of the andragogy method on school principals in developing motivation, leadership and communication after attending education training and strengthening school principals

School Principal Strengthening Education and Training is an activity coordinated by the Directorate General of Teachers and Education Personnel through the Directorate of Educational Personnel Development involving the School Principals Development and Empowerment Institute (LPPKS), Education and Training Organizing Institutions (LPD), Provincial/District/City Education Offices, and educational units. education organized by the community. (Ministry of National Education, 2011) In formal education andragogy is often used in the learning process at the level or level of upper secondary education. However, in applying the

concept, the principle of andragogy in the learning process does not absolutely have to be based on the form, unit level or level of education, but the most important thing is based on the readiness of students to learn. This condition occurs because we assume that all students, students (learning citizens) are adults who are assumed to have an active ability to plan the direction of learning, have materials, think about the best way to learn, analyze and conclude and be able to benefit from learning. or from an educational process. (Kamil, 2015). The implementation of the training program is a series of learning during the training process. The implementation of the training consists of several things, namely: background of activities, training objectives, costs, time and place of training, training schedule, methods, techniques and learning media, rules and learning resources. (Safitri and Yusiyaka, 2020).

Andragogy is a form of learning that is able to produce learning targets (graduates) who can direct themselves and are able to become teachers for themselves. With these advantages andragogy becomes the foundation in the learning process of non-formal education. This happens because non-formal education learning formulas are directed at target conditions that emphasize improving life, providing skills and abilities to solve problems experienced, especially in the life and life of the target in the midst of society. In other concepts andragogy is often defined as adult education or adult learning. The definition of adult education refers to the condition of adult learners in terms of physical (biological), legal, social and psychological dimensions. The term adult is based on the completeness of physical conditions as well as age and psychology, besides that adults can play a role in accordance with the demands of the task from their status. Maturity in a person includes: *age, psychological maturity, and social roles*. (Elias, John.L. and Meriam, Sharan, 1990) What is meant by adult according to age, is every person who turns 21 years old (even though he is not married) (Hiryanto, 2017). Adults seen from the point of view of the biological dimension can also be seen from the physical aspect, where adult humans have distinctive characteristics such as: being able to choose a life partner, ready to marry, and reproduce (*reproductive function*). (Kamil, 2015)

According to Yudrik Jahja, the term adult refers to an organism that has matured. But generally refers to humans. An adult individual is an individual who is no longer in the childhood phase and has become a complete man or woman. After experiencing childhood, an individual will experience a period where he has completed his growth and requires him to be involved with other adult individuals in society. When compared to the previous period, adulthood is the longest phase in an individual's life. (Jahja, 2011). Considering that adults have different characteristics from the characteristics of young students, then in the educational process, there are several things that are taken in its implementation, including:

- 1) Creating a conducive learning climate, among others; a) arrangement of the physical environment such as arrangement of equipment adapted to the conditions of adults, hearing aids and clay adapted to the physical condition of adults, arrangement of the room, setting of tables, chairs and other equipment should allow for social interaction, b) setting of the social and psychological environment, this environment should make adults feel accepted, valued and supported, develop a friendly, informal, relaxed atmosphere, build a spirit of togetherness,
- 2) Diagnosing learning needs, involving stakeholders who are directly affected by the implementation of their education, build the desired model, provide the required experience,
- 3) Planning process, involve students in preparing training plans,
- 4) Formulating goals, namely about the behavior that will be produced to meet the needs of students,
- 5) Develop a general model, more adult education through discussion, both small and large groups Determine the learning materials and techniques, the material is more emphasized on real experience, adapted to needs and oriented to practical applications, the methods and techniques chosen must avoid techniques which is the transfer of knowledge from the facilitator to the students, is more participatory. (Sunhaji,

2013)

In the process of increasing the capacity and quality of human resources that are very strategic and tactical, not only through formal education. Education in a broad sense is not only in the form of formal education for children aged at work institutions, but more than that, education also includes various efforts to increase the capacity of individuals and society (adults) to live a better life. Learning activities can be carried out in the form of education and training courses, or learning activities carried out by community organizations. Another opinion states that learning is a relatively permanent change in a behavioral tendency as a result of practice or practice. (Islamiah, 2016).

Principals have a strategic role in improving the quality, relevance and competitiveness of education. Principals of schools/madrasahs also have an important role in the effort to form intelligent and competitive Indonesian people through their sincerity and creativity in managing the schools they are responsible for. As a consequence, school/madrasah principals must be people who are selected in terms of qualifications and competencies as referred to by Permendiknas Number 13 of 2007 (Ministry of National Education, 2011). In principle, the andragogy learning method must pay attention to the following:

- 1) Physically, psychologically and physiologically visual and auditory health, the main key to successful learning is when the receptor organs are in perfect health, such as the visual function must be in normal condition as well as the auditory function, because the role of visual and auditory has a strategic role for the creation of this process. memory comprehension and storage,
- 2) Based on knowledge and experience as well as needs, the educational process for adults is a good engagement between the student's learning experience and the knowledge possessed, this combination of experience and knowledge is used as the basis for the implementation of various learning activities.
- 3) Persuasive, motivator and stimulus, learning activities in adults are and emphasize awareness and encouragement on the basis of intrinsic stimulation based on learning needs (Djumena, 2016)

The Indonesian Encyclopedia states that strategy in the world of education is defined as *a plan, method, or series of activities designed to achieve a particular educational goal*. Thus, learning strategies can be interpreted as planning that contains a series of activities designed to achieve certain educational goals. There are two things that must be observed from the above understanding, (1) the learning strategy is an action plan/series of activities including the use of methods and the utilization of various resources/strengths in learning. This means that the preparation of a strategy has only arrived at the process of preparing a work plan but has not yet reached the action, (2) the strategy is prepared to achieve certain goals, meaning that the direction of all strategic planning decisions is the achievement of goals. According to Kemp learning strategy is a learning activity that must be done by teachers and students so that learning objectives can be achieved effectively and efficiently. In line with the opinion above, Dick and Carey also stated that a learning strategy is a set of learning materials and procedures that are used together to produce learning outcomes for students (Yusri, 2017).

In adult learning, many methods are applied. According to Budiwan: "For the success of this kind of learning, whatever method is applied it should consider the factors and infrastructure available to achieve the ultimate goal of learning, namely so that participants can have a quality learning experience. It is a big mistake if, in this case, the supervisor inappropriately determines the use of the method only because of his own considerations, namely using the method he deems the easiest, or only because he wants to be admired by the participants in the class or there may be a tendency to only master one particular method." (Budiwan, 2018). In addition, adults can be taught to be more active if they feel they are involved in learning activities, especially if they are involved in contributing thoughts and ideas that make them feel valuable and have self-esteem in front of their friends. This means that adults will learn better when their personal opinions are respected, and will be happier if they can share their thoughts and express their thoughts, rather than the supervisor just cramping their own theories and ideas on them. (Maemunah, Sri, Abdul, Syaharuddin, Agus, Irma, 2020).

The andragogy approach implemented in education and training to strengthen school principals is carried out considering that the participants who take part in this activity are on average over 35 (thirty five) years old, so the learning strategy must be adapted to their circumstances. Adult learning is seen as a transformational adult, namely changing (*modifying*), relearning (*relearning*), updating (*up dating*), and replacing (*replacing*). (Roy, 2019), so it is hoped that the learning outcomes achieved are more optimal. The learning process in the implementation of education and training uses an andragogy approach, emphasizing participants to know new things that they previously did not know through the following stages:

1) Motivation

Motivation is a desire to achieve something. While short-term motivation in the form of interest in learning at that time, and long-term motivation can be in the form of a desire to get good test scores, the desire to achieve, and so on.

2) Attention to lessons

Participants must be able to focus their attention on the lesson. If this does not happen, the learning process will experience obstacles. The attention of this participant is very dependent on the supervisor. If the teacher can attract the attention of the participants, their attention will be high. This can be done by educators by: varying the tempo of teaching, tone of voice, movements, and teaching techniques. Second, the insertion of a short break at a certain moment. And finally, ask and answer questions.

3) Receive and remember

After paying attention to the lesson, a participant will understand and accept and store in his mind. This stage of receiving and remembering must occur in the person who is learning. There are several factors that can influence this reception and recall, such as structure, meaning, repetition of lessons, and intervention.

4) Reproduction

In the learning process, a person must not only receive and remember new information, but he must be able to rediscover anything that has been received (reproduction).

5) Generalization

Participants must be able to apply what they have learned elsewhere and in a wider scope. Generalization can also be interpreted as applying what has been learned from one situation to another (Roy, 2019).

Learning activities for adults aim to lead individuals to become personal or find their identity. In terms of learning or education is a *process of becoming a person*. It is not a process of formation or *process of being shaped*, namely the process of controlling and manipulating to conform to other people. The implications of the assumptions of andragogic teaching are:

- 1) The learning process for participants is more emphasized on techniques that are tapping into their experiences such as discussions, studies cases, critical incident methods, simulations, role playing, demonstrations, project methods, and the like.
- 2) Teaching and learning are accentuated on practical application.
- 3) The teaching and learning process prioritize learning in groups with great respect for individual differences.
- 4) Students who have diverse experiences are usually also very closed to new ideas or alternative thinking. For this reason, teachers should help overcome this by finding new approaches and techniques that suit their self-image. (Yusri, 2017)

Respondents' responses in the implementation of the training using the andragogy approach method, namely by being active in the learning process, both in discussions, understanding in the various materials presented, as well as a good response from participants because the media used in the learning process is

supported by suitable media. able to help participants understand the material well. Likewise, the responses given by participants to the widyaswara were able to encourage participants to encourage active and interactive learning, both in carrying out their duties as tutors, and as partners during this training.

The process of implementing the training begins with fostering intimacy between participants and participants with the instructor, because each class is accompanied by 2 teachers and 2 class committee members who help with participant administration. The training materials provided during this training consist of 7 (seven) sections which include: 1) Instructions for the Implementation of Education and Training for Principal Strengthening; 2) Technical Guidelines for Principal Strengthening Education and Training; 3) Handbook; 4) Principal Strengthening Education and Training Module; 5) Training tools; 6) Assessment formats; 7) Pre and post test questions. (Ministry of National Education, 2011).

The determination of the number of teachers as much as 2 people in team teaching is based on the following considerations:

- 1) The characteristics of adult education (andragogy) are principally directed at developing the understanding, knowledge and experience of participants so that learning patterns are designed through various discussion activities, group work, and presentations, and are not dominated by giving lectures and information.
- 2) Considering that discussion activities and especially group work are carried out simultaneously (parallel), facilitation from the teacher is also carried out in parallel. Therefore, the presence of 2 (two) teachers in one class is very necessary.
- 3) Another consideration is the number of participants as many as 40 people and 30 people need more varied handling and learning methods so that the presence of 2 training instructors allows this to be done.
- 4) In practice, 2 education and training teachers work together in the form of team teaching, where one training teacher and another education and training teacher jointly manage learning, both in facilitating the implementation of discussions, group work, practice, simulations, and presentations, as well as in providing reinforcement. In the event that one training teacher provides information or reinforcement, the other training teacher will act as an observer to observe the participants' activities. (Ministry of National Education, 2011).

Learning is divided into 5 groups; each group consists of 8 people with 1 group leader. Each training subject has an assignment that must be submitted to be assessed by the teacher. The learning process during training and education is carried out with explanations from the teacher, reviewing modules, working on structured assignments and presenting the results of assignments as well as assessments from teachers. The training is carried out for 8 (eight) days, this activity is calculated based on the JP, where 1 JP is equivalent to 60 minutes consisting of general activities which include:

- 1) Policy of the Ministry of Education and Culture for 2 hours of lessons (JP),
- 2) activity orientation for 1 JP,
- 3) Technical Explanation of Training for Principal Candidates and Strengthening of Principals for 2 JP,
- 4) Management Information System Functional Educational Training for 2 JP, so that the total general activity lasts for 7 seven hours of lessons (JP), after general activities are completed, followed by core activities for 61 JP, which consists of:
 - (1) Integration of Character Values in Training Materials for 2 JP,
 - (2) Learning Oriented to Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) for 2 JP,
 - (3) Analysis of Leadership and Entrepreneurship Module for 7 JP,
 - (4) Analysis of the Managerial Competency Module for 24 JP consisting of:
 - (a) Management Analysis Techniques,
 - (b) Preparation and Development of School Work Plans,
 - (c) School Financial Management,

- (d) Management of Educators and Education Personnel,
 - (e) Management of School Facilities and Infrastructure,
 - (f) Student Management,
 - (g) Curriculum Management,
 - (h) School Administration Management,
 - (i) Digital Literacy and Utilization of Information and Communication Technology in Learning,
 - (j) Production and Service-Based Learning Management
- (5) Analysis of the Supervision Competency Module, for 10 JP consisting of:
- (a) Supervision and Assessment of Teacher Performance
 - (b) Supervision and Performance Assessment of Education Personnel
 - (c) Continuing Professional Development Plan
- (6) Analysis of Monitoring and Evaluation Module for 4 JP
- (7) Analysis of School Development Materials Based on 8 SNPs and Follow Up Plans for 2 JP
- (8) Simulation of IN-1 Facilitation (CKS Training) and Face-to-face (KS Strengthening) for 4 JP
- (9) Simulation of OJL Facilitation (CKS Training) for 4 JP
- (10) IN-2 Facilitation Simulation (CKS Training) for 2 JP

b) The effectiveness of the andragogy method in increasing the motivation of the principal

Applying the andragogy method in the learning process during the implementation of training and education for strengthening principals is based on their readiness to receive lessons at the secondary education level and above. In applying this concept, participants do not absolutely have to refer to the form, unit level or level of education. This is because the teachers and widyasaras consider that these participants are adults and have active abilities in planning the direction of learning, completing learning materials, trying to learn better, and being able to analyze and make conclusions during the learning process so that they can benefit from the training to be applied in the school he leads.

According to Hiryanto, "Guidance and motivation given by teachers and widyasaras are facilitators, not tutors, so that the relationships created are more multi-communication. Therefore, andragogy is a form of learning that is able to give birth to learning targets (graduates) who can direct themselves and are able to become teachers for themselves. With these advantages' andragogy becomes the foundation in the learning process of non-formal education. This happens because in non-formal education, the learning formula is directed at target conditions that emphasize improving life, providing skills and abilities to solve problems experienced, especially in the life and lives of the target in the midst of society" (Hiryanto, 2009)

The enthusiasm of the participants during learning using the andragogy method was applied by the principal after they finished attending the training to increase motivation in leading their school. Because the motivation to improve the quality of education is absolutely owned by the principal in leading the school. The increased motivation of school principals after carrying out the training was answered in the results of questionnaires and interviews conducted by researchers. The desire to increase the motivation of school principals after participating in carrying out this training can be seen from the results of the answers which state that they are serious in carrying out their duties as principals because the main goal is to improve the quality and quantity of the schools they lead, in addition, in terms of discipline carried out by the principal to be an example for teachers and other school members. The principal also provides motivation and encouragement to teachers to improve and develop their abilities, especially in motivating teachers to continue their education to a higher level and develop learning methods and media, so that it is hoped that they will improve the achievements of their students, so that the integrity and quality of the school will increase. . And to improve the performance of teachers and students, principals provide rewards in the form of grades and in other forms. Besides that, the principal also makes and formulates the program contained in the school's vision and mission as well as a clear division of tasks to the teachers so that they jointly carry out the agreed vision and mission to improve the quality and quality of education.

c. The effectiveness of the andragogy method in improving the principal's leadership style

In improving the leadership of school principals, from the results of this study, the effectiveness of the andragogy approach in school leadership style, after participating in the training, the following results were obtained, in carrying out responsibilities and making policies, principals carried out wisely in accordance with their capacity as leaders which had an impact on increasing performance. teachers, as well as in helping with difficulties when the teacher carries out his duties, the principal will always be ready to help. In communicating, the principal always maintains harmony, including in providing motivation and positive input to anyone, both within the school environment and outside the school environment, the principal is also always ready to accept criticism and suggestions submitted to him, so that interactions in the work environment support each other for the sake of mutual support. progress and improvement of the quality of learning in the school environment he leads.

In a book entitled Learning Psychology, Syaiful Bahri provides a definition: "Leadership style is the result to be achieved by a successful leader. Leadership does not mean that an administrator must become a leader or a head must turn into a leader, but the most important thing is how the principal influences all elements in the school in achieving goals. Therefore, an effective principal's leadership style is a leader who can feel what is needed by providing motivation so that teachers can perform well in achieving the goals of the school's vision and mission. There are three leadership styles, namely:

1) Autocratic Autocratic leadership is a leader who makes his own decisions. The leader assumes full responsibility and authority. Autocratic leadership is a leadership style in which all control is held by the leader. Leaders who use this style tend to be arbitrary towards their subordinates. The characteristics of an autocratic leader are:

- (1) Regards the organization he leads as private property,
 - (2) Treating subordinates as mere tools,
 - (3) Do not want to accept opinions, suggestions and criticism,
 - (4) How to move subordinates with a coercive approach and is fault-finding/punishing. (Syaiful Bahri, 2002)
- 2) Democratic

According to (M. Ngalim, 2006), democratic or participatory leadership is a leader who consults with groups on issues that interest them where they can contribute something.

3) Lazes-faire (Freedom)

This leadership is a leader who gives power to subordinates, the group can develop its own goals and solve its own problems, there is no direction from the leader. This style is usually useless but can be effective in highly motivated professional groups. Leaders who use this leadership style tend to be principle less and uncreative because all control is given to subordinates. So there is no direction from the leader. (Rukmana, 2019).

With the application of the andragogy method in training and training to strengthen principals, it is able to improve the leadership style of principals, because in practice there are many problems that arise during the principal's leadership. So that the leadership of school principals is further improved after they take part in training and training to strengthen principals, because they apply the knowledge gained after participating in this training activity, because during the learning process of this training, learning tendencies are oriented towards problem solving. This is because learning for adults is a necessity to face the problems faced in everyday life, especially in relation to the functions and social roles of adults. In addition, this difference in assumptions is also due to differences in time perspectives. For adults, learning is more to be used or utilized in the immediate future. This has implications for the nature of learning or training materials for adults, namely that these materials should be practical and can be immediately applied in everyday reality. (Wasposito, 2009).

In improving their leadership style, from the results of the author's interviews with the principal, they provide instructions and direct teachers and students in the learning process, this is done so that the principal knows firsthand, what problems are complaints, whether experienced by teachers or participants students in the learning

process, as well as the root causes of problems that occur during the learning process, so that the principal can anticipate and minimize these problems, so that the learning process can run well.

In solving problems that arise during the learning process, the principal also accepts complaints from teachers, and resolves them by deliberation before taking appropriate action to overcome these problems. This is what the principal does in responding to complaints from his students. The principal always discusses with his students about the complaints and problems they experience during the learning process and accommodates these complaints and discusses them with the teacher, so that the teacher is also involved in solving the problems that befell his students. If students feel reluctant to submit their complaints, the principal also provides a suggestion box for students in submitting complaints about the learning process accompanied by clear information, what subjects and who the teacher is, so that the principal can immediately take action and consult with the teacher concerned about the complaint. The effectiveness of the principal's leadership depends on how the principal can use the appropriate leadership style.

According to Mulyasa, 2007 with the theory of the flow of goals (*part-Goal Theory*) suggests that: "there are four leadership styles that will be displayed by leaders and subordinates in the leadership process, namely directive leaders (directing), supportive (helping), participative (participation) and Goal Orientation (Achievement oriented)". Effective whether or not the leadership style depends on how the leadership style adapts to mature (matured) subordinates. (Islamiah, 2016) According to Raihani, there are four (4) principal leadership styles, including:

- 1) Instructional style or directing such as giving instructions to teachers and giving instructions to students in the learning process.
- 2) Consultation or deliberation style such as consulting with teachers in solving school problems and deliberation to reach a consensus.
- 3) Participatory or democratic styles, such as participation and democracy,
- 4) The style of delegation or delegation of authority such as giving teaching authority and giving authority regarding attitude towards students (Raihani, 2010)

d. The effectiveness of the andragogy method in improving principal communication

Good communication between the principal and teachers, education staff, students and the surrounding environment is one of the important points that must be considered by the principal. Principal communication is the process of delivering information (messages) to teachers and being able to carry out that information to students. The purpose of communication is general in nature, while the purpose of education is specific. The purpose of education will be achieved if the process is communicative. If the learning process is not communicative, it is impossible for the educational goals to be achieved.

The principal as a source of information in schools is needed by teachers, so that what is conveyed can be implemented for the development of teachers themselves and also for students. From the results of this study, in communicating with all school members, the principal is able to express his opinion honestly, both negative and positive opinions, but in conveying negative opinions it is aimed directly at individuals, besides that the principal always provides support to teachers. Teachers who have ideas in developing learning methods. Communication is realized through symbols or symbols, generally in the form of words, pictures, and gesture actions such as nodding, eye movements, raising eyebrows, and so on. The failure of communication in a particular organization can be seen from: (1) whether the purpose of the message conveyed was achieved or not; (2) whether the communication tools or informational materials that have been symbolized in the symbols convey the message or not; and (3) whether the recipient of the message can understand what was ordered or not. Building effective communication is not easy, there are many conditions that must be considered by communicators to achieve communication goals correctly. The type of communication that will be discussed is divided into four types,

namely communication with oneself, interpersonal communication, public communication, and mass communication. (Fatimah, Djailani, and, Khairuddin, 2015)

According to Arifin Anwar: "Principal communication is the process of delivering information (messages) to teachers and being able to carry out that information to students. The principal as a source of information in schools is needed by teachers, so that what is conveyed can be implemented for the development of teachers themselves and also for students. From the results of this study, in communicating with all school members, the principal is able to express his opinion honestly, both negative and positive opinions, but in conveying negative opinions it is aimed directly at individuals, besides that the principal always provides support to teachers. teachers who have ideas in developing learning methods".

With good communication among the citizens of this school, it will improve the quality and quality of the school education they lead. Improving communication well is not only done with residents as if it were, but also with parents/guardians of students. Principals must be willing to accept criticism, complaints and suggestions from them. From the research results obtained, the establishment of good communication between the principal and all school residents, with the environment as well as with parents/guardians of students is well established, the principal always greets teachers, education staff, and also students, be it in the school environment and outside the school environment. Headmaster also always recommends that homeroom teachers always communicate with parents, so that students' progress in learning at school is known by parents / guardians of students, and school principals always accept criticism, suggestions, complaints and input, both from teachers and parents / student guardian.

The principal also provides opportunities for students to express their complaints directly, whether it is about difficulties in the learning process, or if there are problems with the teacher. If this student does not dare to convey it directly, the principal also provides a suggestion box, where if this student submits a complaint, it must be equipped with the name, class, and type of complaint related to the learning process. And only the designated principal and teacher have the right to open the suggestion box, so that the principal can directly respond, respond and resolve the complaint, by consensus and deliberation.

IV. CONCLUSION

The implementation of learning using the andragogy method in training and training for strengthening school principals batch IX at P4TK Business Tourism which was attended by school principals in Banten Province, could be understood by the principal, this was observed directly by researchers during this activity, all participants were able to follow the stages of the activity well and orderly, according to a predetermined schedule, as well as the widyasarana who guides the implementation of this activity, who can guide and carry out their duties well, so that when this research was carried out a year later, it had an impact on increasing the motivation of the principal in motivating teachers to work together develop and improve the ability of teachers in improving the quality and quality of the schools they lead. The increasing motivation of principals in improving the quality and quality of the schools they lead is done by providing and assisting teachers in improving their teaching abilities, also motivating teachers in developing methods, media in learning and curriculum, as well as motivating teachers to continue their education to a higher level.

In improving his leadership style after participating in the training and training to strengthen school principals, what he does is responsible for implementing policies, whether issued by the central government, regional governments, from the local education office, as well as policies made by the principal himself. and the quality of the school he leads is in line with the expectations of the government and society. The responsibility of the principal in developing policies that must be carried out by teachers and school residents is also based on careful consideration, this is done so that the duties of teachers as education implementers can be in accordance with their capacities, in addition to implementing policies, principals are also always ready to help the difficulties of teachers in solving problems. carry out their duties. Communication with all residents in the school environment, as well as outside the school environment is also well established,

besides that the principal is always ready to accept input, criticism and suggestions, both from parents / guardians of students and from the environment outside the school.

After attending training and training on strengthening principals using the andragogy method, it is hoped that the principal will always develop his abilities in other fields, be it for development in the fields of facilities and infrastructure, infrastructure, entrepreneurship, character development, managerial, comparative studies to more advanced educational institutions. quality, as well as in other fields, this will be very beneficial for teachers and students in the future. By developing these abilities, it is hoped that the quality and quality of the graduates produced will increase. Even for the Pamulang University Principal Education and Training Organization, it is better to evaluate all training participants, not only for class IX participants, this is to determine the success and effectiveness of the education and training implementation that has been carried out so that in the future it can be more professional in its implementation

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